

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Effects of agri-environment schemes on farm-level eco-efficiency measures: Empirical evidence from EU countries

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Abstract

The European Union (EU) budget allocated to agri-environmental schemes (AES) has increased consistently over the past 20 years. European citizens should expect effective spending of these public funds, so investigation of the effects of these schemes on both environmental benefits and farm efficiency is warranted. We examine the effects of European agri-environmental schemes on farm-level eco-efficiency. Our analysis combines data envelopment analysis and impact assessment methods to evaluate the impact of scheme payments on eco-efficiency measures. Our results suggest that there is considerable scope for eco-efficiency improvements, both for dairy and crop production. Results also show that the average change in eco-efficiency scores does not vary significantly between AES participants and non-participants, which questions the effectiveness of present AES.

KEYWORDS

agri-environment programmes, data envelopment analysis, eco-efficiency, environmental damages, impact evaluation

JEL CLASSIFICATION

C23, D22, Q12, Q18, Q57

1 | INTRODUCTION

Over the last century, several factors—including public subsidies and technical innovations—have led to agricultural intensification. As a result of new developments in agricultural production management, farmers became very successful at increasing agricultural yields and production, and hence lower food prices. But these achievements have come at the cost of increased damage to the environment.

Public awareness of environmental problems associated with food production has been growing over the last decades (European Commission, 2010; FAO, 2017). As a response to these concerns,

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in early 1990, the European Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) introduced financial support for the member states to design and implement agri-environment schemes (AES), also called agri-environment-climate schemes (AECS), through their Rural Development Programmes (RDP). AES are payments made to farmers who voluntarily adopt more sustainable agricultural practices. Starting from 1993, the EU budget allocated to scheme payments has risen substantially. The overall¹ expenditure for the RDP in 2007–2013 was €96.3 billion (about 20% of the total CAP budget) and reached €161 billion during the period 2014–2020. The AES payments accounted for the biggest share (23.6%) of the Rural Development funding.

According to the last EU official data on participation (2013), the average share of agricultural area (UAA) under AES in EU-27 was 26%, with substantial variation between countries, ranging from 92% of UAA in Luxembourg to less than 5% in Bulgaria (Eurostat, 2017). In terms of UAA under AES, measures for organic farming, the management of landscape, pastures, and High Nature Value farmland were the most popular (39% of the total UAA under AES in EU-27). Compared to 2013, when the UAA committed to organic farming was 5.7%, organic farming in 2019 covered 8.5% of UAA (European Commission, 2019). Around 67% of this area received CAP support.

Despite the increasing public expenditure on AES, there are still concerns about the capacity of these measures to deliver the expected results. To respond to European citizens' demand for more effective spending of EU budgets, it is crucial to investigate the effectiveness of agri-environmental measures for delivering environmental benefits while improving farms' economic efficiency. To date, still little is known about the environmental and economic effectiveness of the AES (Hasler et al., 2022). Most of the existing literature focuses on the achievement of the environmental objectives pursued by the measures, while not taking into account the effects of AES on farmers' economic performance.

In recent years, the concept of eco-efficiency has gained popularity among researchers because it allows investigating how the production of more goods and services can be achieved while using minimal resources and causing less environmental damage. In contrast to the concept of sustainability (whose definition remains imprecise), eco-efficiency can more easily be quantified by ratios between a firm's economic value-added and environmental damage generated through the production process. In the context of AES, eco-efficiency measurements can be a useful tool for comparing the efficiency of AES participating to non-participating farms in terms of environmental and economic performance.

We use the non-parametric data envelopment analysis (DEA) model to estimate farm-level eco-efficiency measures. This aggregates several environmental damages to contribute to the eco-efficiency measure. These relationships are likely to be nonlinear, and difficult to assess (Kuosmanen & Kortelainen, 2005). While stochastic frontier analysis (SFA) can be used rather than DEA, we argue that this approach does not fully capture the complex nature of the relationship between environmental damages and ecological damage.

There is a growing body of research which estimates farm-level eco-efficiency measures (e.g., Bonfiglio et al., 2017; Cortés et al., 2020; Godoy-Durán et al., 2017; Pérez Urdiales et al., 2016; Stepień et al., 2021). Although a significant amount of literature on the environmental impact of agri-environmental schemes exists, relatively few attempts have been made to investigate their economic impact (e.g., Bokusheva et al., 2012; Chabé-Ferret & Subervie, 2013).

We contribute to research about the joint impact of AES on farm economic and environmental performance by estimating the effect of AES participation on farm-level eco-efficiency. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first paper that combines non-parametric data envelopment analysis with impact evaluation methods to assess whether farm-level eco-efficiency is affected by AES participation. Our approach uses several years of observations while controlling for possible selection bias issues arising from observed and unobserved characteristics. This evaluation can show policy-makers

¹This includes both funds from EAFRD and the national budgets of EU countries.

whether agri-environment programmes are having the expected effects, and (by comparison between different AES packages) improve effectiveness of government initiatives.

The related literature typically investigates these questions for one country or one region. In this study, we include in the analysis four diverse EU member states: Germany, France, Italy and the Netherlands. To do so, we rely on the comparable European Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) data over the period 2006–2011 to estimate our models and determine the impact of AES on farms' eco-efficiency measures. By using this database, researchers can make meaningful cross-national comparisons and circumvent the challenge of comparing results from studies that employ different methods and data sets.

The following section provides an outline of previous research on the relationship between AES and farms' environmental and economic performance. The methodological approaches are presented in the third section. The fourth section focuses on data and empirical implementation. The fifth section reports the main results of our analysis, and the last section provides some conclusions.

2 | LITERATURE REVIEW

Agri-environmental schemes are the EU's most important policy tools to mitigate the environmental impact of agriculture. These schemes are farm-level payments made by the EU and its member states to those farmers choosing to implement agri-environment measures included in Rural Development Programmes. The programmes and associated measures have been mandatory for member states since 1992, reflecting European agro-environmental priorities but designed at the regional level to reflect the complexity and regional diversity of both farming and eco-systems.

Agri-environmental schemes require farmers to adopt specific management practices for a 5-year contract. In return, farmers are compensated for the cost incurred and productivity losses. Over the years, there has been increasing attention on the effectiveness of these schemes in delivering environmental benefits and their impact on farming. Most papers on AES have a national or regional focus, with an emphasis on the ecological benefits (Uthes & Matzdorf, 2013). Some analyse the drivers that influence farmers' adoption of agri-environmental contracts (e.g., Defrancesco et al., 2007; Dessart et al., 2019; Giovanopoulou et al., 2011), and others explore the schemes' effectiveness (e.g., Mary, 2013) and farmer's production choices (e.g., Laukkanen & Nauges, 2012).

To study the causal effects, researchers have increasingly applied propensity score matching (PSM) and/or a difference-in-differences (DID) estimator. Since participation in the schemes is voluntary, adoption might well be driven by farmers' preferences, attitudes and circumstances. Because of this selection bias, the comparison between participating and non-participating farms may not represent the causal impact of the AES. To overcome this issue, econometric techniques are used to identify comparable participant and non-participant units with similar observed and unobserved characteristics by using DID estimators, which can be combined with matching (Heckman et al., 1997).

To study the effect of AES on individual farmers' behaviour, Pufahl and Weiss (2009) used a PSM approach to analyse the impact of AES on the input and output levels of German farms. Their findings indicate that AES payments have a positive and significant effect. Sauer et al. (2012) used a directional distance-based and a matching technique to investigate the effects of different agri-environmental schemes on individual farmers' behaviour for a sample of UK cereal farms. They found that farmers were able to adjust their farming strategies to the AES conditions. According to their analysis, the farms participating in the schemes tend to become less specialised and more diversified in their production structure. Chabé-Ferret and Subervie (2013) used a PSM-DID method with a structural household model to estimate and compare the effects of five agri-environmental schemes in France. They observed that AES promoting crop diversity resulted in an additional crop in the rotation, and was also associated with a reduction of cropped area. D'Alberto et al. (2018)

combined a statistical matching and propensity score matching to conduct an impact evaluation of AES in the Emilia-Romagna Region in Italy. Their results highlight that participation in specific schemes has a significant impact on farmers' decisions to reduce both the rent-in land and the crop diversity of farms.

Some studies examined AES participation effects on farm economic performance. Mennig and Sauer (2020) applied a DID propensity score matching technique to investigate if participation has an unforeseen impact on farms' productivity in Bavaria. Their findings indicate that the AES measures designed for dairy farms have a negative impact on farm productivity. Baráth et al. (2020) applied a similar approach to a sample of Slovenian farms to examine the effect of different types of subsidies, including agri-environmental measures, on the different components of total factor productivity (TFP). They find no significant association between AES payments and TFP growth.

Most ex-post environmental evaluations rely on farm surveys (Primdahl et al., 2010), which are usually based on small-scale samples and are often limited to one region or one type of scheme. For instance, Cisilino et al. (2019) studied the effects of organic farming measures in the Marche Region in Italy by comparing the environmental and economic performance of organic and conventional farms. They combined a DID with a matching procedure to observe the effects on nitrogen and phosphorus use. Their results suggest that organic farms outperform conventional ones in terms of environmental performance, whereas the findings on economic performance do not confirm that organic agriculture is as competitive as conventional. Recently, Bertoni et al. (2020) applied coarsened exact matching to analyse the effect of three AES implemented in the Lombardy Region (Italy). Their results suggest that AES payments are effective in improving farms' environmental performance. However, the authors highlight the high cost of implementation compared to the benefits they provide. Nevertheless, large-scale evidence may provide a more comprehensive assessment of AES effectiveness.

Arata and Sckokai (2016) are the only authors that use a DID with PSM estimator in a cross-national study of the effects of the agri-environmental payments on farmers' environmental and economic performance. They considered, among others, the AES effects on farm income, employment, number of crops grown, and share of grassland. Their results suggest that AES participation affects both farmer's input use and farm economic outcomes, although with significant differences between countries. They also observed that the impact of the payments is mostly determined by the proportion of the AES payment in the total farm revenue.

Closely related to the need to define a measure that reflects both ecological and economic goals of farms, the concept of eco-efficiency refers to the production of more goods and services while using minimal resources and causing less environmental damage. It became popular in 1993 following the report of the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (Schmidheiny, 1993), and has been widely recognised as a key strategic component of sustainability (OECD, 1998). The concept provides a workable approach to sustainability that may be used to assess whether producers optimise their use of resources to achieve their economic and environmental goals (Picazo-Tadeo et al., 2011). According to Kuosmanen and Kortelainen (2005), measuring eco-efficiency remains relevant for two reasons: (i) eco-efficiency improvement can be considered the most cost-effective way to reduce environmental damages; (ii) policy measures that promote eco-efficiency are typically easier to implement than policies that restrict economic performance.

The main advantage of data envelopment analysis (Korhonen & Luptacik, 2004) is that no prior assumptions are needed about the functional relationship between inputs and outputs. Although originally conceived to assess the performance of decision-making units based on marketable inputs and outputs, it has also been used to address the environmental consequences of production processes by taking into account 'bad' inputs and outputs (Førsund, 2009; Murty et al., 2012).

An extensive empirical literature exists on applying DEA to estimate eco-efficiency in a wider range of sectors (De Koeijer et al., 2002; Korhonen & Luptacik, 2004; Kortelainen & Kuosmanen, 2007; Zhang et al., 2008). Several authors have used the concept of eco-efficiency to evaluate European farm-

ers. Among them, Iribarren et al. (2011) and Cortés et al. (2020) who combined life cycle assessment and DEA to assess the eco-efficiency of dairy farms in the region of Galicia (Spain). Picazo-Tadeo et al. (2011) estimated the eco-efficiency of a group of Spanish farms in Castilla and León, using DEA. Pérez Urdiales et al. (2016) looked at how farmers' socio-economic characteristics and attitudes influence Spanish dairy farmers' eco-efficiency. Bonfiglio et al. (2017) and Stępień et al. (2021) used FADN data and DEA to estimate damage-specific eco-efficiency scores of arable farms in Italy and Poland, respectively.

There have been some attempts at linking environmental efficiency to AES payments, including, in particular, work by Dakpo and Latruffe (2016) and Skevas et al. (2018). Both studies examined the potential influence of some contextual factors in explaining environmental efficiency scores, including agri-environmental subsidies. The first used a second-stage regression analysis to assess the impact of agri-environmental schemes on greenhouse gas emissions and farm technical efficiency of French beef cattle farms. The second examined the impact of AES payments (along with other factors) on the environmental performance of Dutch dairy farms using a hyperbolic distance function. Such an approach is limited in the sense that it only helps to identify whether a change in farm performance is associated with a change in some independent variables and does not consider the effectiveness of a particular intervention. Beltrán-Estevé et al. (2012) assessed the impact of a specific agri-environmental scheme on the farm-level eco-efficiency of farms in Castilla y León (Spain), though did not account for selection bias.

We use the European FADN dataset to compute eco-efficiency scores for both dairy and field crops farms, and for different EU countries. In doing so, we account for the heterogeneous effects of AES across different EU member states and farming systems. The use of eco-efficiency measures to assess whether AES payments are effective or not provides a useful policy tool for the development and implementation of farm-level sustainability indicators.

3 | METHODOLOGY

Our analytical framework follows a three-step approach. First, we use propensity score matching to control for potential selection bias arising from observable characteristics, to identify observably similar (matched) farms apart from their use of AES. We then perform a data envelopment analysis to compute farm-level eco-efficiency scores for the matched observations. Finally, the average treatment effect of AES participation on farms' eco-efficiency scores is derived by applying a difference-in-difference specification. We explain our estimation strategy as follows.

3.1 | Propensity score matching

In non-experimental research, matching is widely used to measure the average effect of a treatment. When evaluating the effect of a non-randomised treatment, the key challenge is to define the counterfactual state, that is, what would have happened to the participants if this programme did not exist. Since only one state is observed for each individual, there is a lack of necessary information to carry out the impact analysis. Moreover, participation in voluntary policy measures, such as agri-environment schemes, may depend on implementation costs and expected benefits, making the treatment assignment non-random and related to both observed and unobserved characteristics (Martin Persson & Alpizar, 2013). To eliminate this selection bias, appropriate methods for constructing a comparison group must be defined. Matching can be used to control for selection bias on the basis of observed characteristics and build a suitable counterfactual or control group.

The idea of matching is to make non-participants similar to those in the treatment group in terms of a set of covariates X . Rosenbaum and Rubin (1983) suggested matching on the propensity score,

$\pi(X) = P(T = 1|X)$. The propensity score is defined as the individual's probability of treatment assignment, conditional on observed covariates X . Then, based on the estimated propensity score, each participant is matched² with a similar non-participant.

Following the completion of the matching procedure, and once comparable participants and non-participant farms have been identified, the second step requires the calculation of the eco-efficiency scores. The programme impact is then estimated as a third step using difference-in-difference.

3.2 | Computation of eco-efficiency

Depending on how environmental pollution is treated, the literature incorporating environmental considerations into traditional frontier-based performance measures may be divided into two groups (Tyteca, 1996, 1997). The first type treats pollution either as unintended output or an input. The resulting studies have labelled this measure 'environmental efficiency' (Reinhard et al., 1999, 2000). The second modelling assumption links economic outcomes to environmental damage rather than traditional inputs, nowadays known as 'frontier eco-efficiency models'. We believe that relying on eco-efficiency measures is particularly relevant in the European agricultural context.

Eco-efficiency can be interpreted as a ratio of economic value added (v^i) and environmental damage $Z(p_n^i)$ (Helminen, 2000; Schmidheiny & Zorraquin, 1996). Thus, the eco-efficiency of farm i can be formally expressed as:

$$\text{Eco - efficiency}^i = \frac{v^i}{Z(p_n^i)} \quad (1)$$

where Z is the aggregator function that integrates environmental damage to generate a specific environmental damage score—that is, $Z(p_n^i) = \sum_{n=1}^N w_n^i p_n^i$, where w_n^i represents the weight given to environmental damage n .

The major difficulty with using this ratio is that appropriate weights must be assigned to each environmental indicator. Data envelopment analysis can be used as an objective weighting method, as it assigns optimal weights³ to each indicator (Kuusmanen & Kortelainen, 2005). The eco-efficiency model is then expressed by the following non-linear programming problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{w_n^i} \{ \text{Eco - efficiency}^i \} &= \frac{v^i}{\sum_{n=1}^N w_n^{i'} p_n^{i'}} \\ &\text{s.t.} \\ \frac{v^i}{\sum_{n=1}^N w_n^{i'} p_n^{i'}} &\leq 1, \quad i = 1, \dots, I \\ w_n^{i'} &\geq 0, \quad n = 1, \dots, N \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

²As we are interested in estimating the effect of agri-environment schemes on farm performance over the period 2006–2011, the matching procedure is only implemented for the pre-treatment period (the base year 2006).

³As suggested by the editor, these weights are only optimal with respect to the reduction in value-added, rather than to the importance of the damage done to the environment. In turn, this might suggest that independent estimates of the costs of environmental damage could also be used to value these 'bad' outputs.

Because this dual representation offers infinite solutions, the optimisation problem must be reformulated in its primal form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \min_{\theta^i, \lambda^i} \{ \text{Eco - efficiency}^i \} &= \theta^i \\
 \text{s.t.} & \\
 v^i &\leq \sum_{i=1}^I \lambda^i v^i \\
 \theta^i p_n^i &\geq \sum_{i=1}^I \lambda^i p_n^i, n = 1, \dots, N \\
 \lambda^i &\geq 0, i = 1, \dots, I
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where λ^i represents the intensity variable that weights all farms to define the eco-efficient frontier. θ^i is the eco-efficiency score quantifying the radial distance between a specific farm and the benchmark frontier. It identifies the eco-efficient farms as the ones for which θ^i is equal to one, whereas farms with a score lower than one are considered eco-inefficient. The eco-efficiency performance indicates the highest possible equiproportional reduction of environmental damage while maintaining the existing level of economic performance.

One of the weaknesses of the eco-efficiency measures obtained from model (3) is that a farm can be located on the efficient frontier although it is Pareto-Koopmans⁴ inefficient, meaning that some environmental damage could still be reduced without affecting the economic value added. According to Charnes et al. (1985), the problem can be overcome using the DEA framework to incorporate surpluses in inputs and deficits in outputs ('slacks'). The approach proposed by Charnes et al. (1985) allows for damage-specific reductions (damage slacks) and the corresponding DEA model can be expressed as follows (Ali & Seiford, 1993; Picazo-Tadeo et al., 2011):

$$\begin{aligned}
 \max_{s_v^i, s_p^i, \lambda^i} \{ S^i \} &= s_v^i + \sum_{n=1}^N s_p^i \\
 \text{s.t.} & \\
 v^i + s_v^i &= \sum_{i=1}^I \lambda^i v^i \\
 \theta^i p_n^i - s_p^i &= \sum_{i=1}^I \lambda^i p_n^i, n = 1, \dots, N \\
 s_v^i, s_p^i &\geq 0, n = 1, \dots, N \\
 \lambda^i &\geq 0, i = 1, \dots, I
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

The slack variables s_p and s_v measuring any excess in environmental damage and deficit in economic value-added, respectively, are introduced. The objective function in model (4) is to maximise the sum of environmental damage excess and economic value added deficits for each farm while holding their radial eco-efficiency ratings at the level calculated from model (3). In terms of interpretation, if the slack variable is positive, it could be claimed that the farm is Farrell efficient, but that additional reductions in environmental damage may still be feasible. Such damage slacks provide useful information about the determinants of economic inefficiency (Zhou et al., 2006). This is an attractive feature of the proposed approach because, in the presence of excess in environmental damage, it identifies farms that could further reduce their environmental impacts.

To assess the impact of AES on the damage-specific eco-efficiency measures, Torgersen's methodology (Torgersen et al., 1996) can be used to compare the potential reduction of environmental

⁴See Koopmans (1951) for Pareto-Koopmans efficiency and Farrell (1957) for radial measures.

damage between participating and non-participating farms. To do so, radial reductions and damage specific excess are aggregated to obtain the overall reduction of damage required to reach the Pareto-Koopmans efficient frontier:

$$R_n^i = (1 - \theta^{*i}) p_n^{i'} + s_{p,n}^{i'} \quad (5)$$

The first term on the right-hand side of model (5) is a measure of proportional reduction in damage, and the other term is a measure of the damage specific excess.

As a precursor to measuring the damage specific eco-efficiency, it is necessary first to estimate the Pareto-Koopman efficient level of damage n :

$$\begin{aligned} R_{n,Pareto-Koopmans}^i &= p_n^{i'} - \left[(1 - \theta^{*i}) p_n^{i'} + s_{p,n}^{i'} \right] \\ &= \theta^{*i} p_n^{i'} - s_{p,n}^{i'} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The estimated parameters in (5) and (6) can be used to compute the damage-specific eco-efficiency. Following the steps outlined in Picazo-Tadeo et al. (2011), the damage specific eco-efficiency measures can be obtained from:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Damage specific eco - efficiency}^i &= \frac{R_{n,Pareto-Koopmans}^i}{p_n^{i'}} \\ &= \theta^{*i} - \frac{s_{p,n}^{i'}}{p_n^{i'}} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

This expression shows that the damage-specific eco-efficiency depends not only on the slack variables, but also on the radial eco-efficiency scores. This means that the damage-specific eco-efficiency measure accounts for the total proportional reduction in that damage required to reach the Pareto-Koopmans efficient frontier. The damage-specific eco-efficiency scores are by construction lower or equal to those obtained from the radial approach. A farm with a damage-specific eco-efficiency score of one is considered to be eco-efficient. However, it cannot reduce its environmental damage without altering its economic value added.

3.3 | Difference-in-difference

While matching techniques control for the selection bias on observables, studies have shown that there may be systematic differences between the outcomes of participants and non-participants, even after conditioning on observables (Heckman et al., 1997). As a result, it can be very restrictive to assume that unobservable characteristics play no role in selection. To overcome this problem, Smith and Todd (2005), suggest combining matching with the DID estimator. Panel data are essential to implement a DID approach. The conditional DID estimator compares the non-participating and participating individuals in terms of outcome changes relative to the outcomes observed for a pre-treatment period. Given that t represents a time period before the start of the programme and t' a time period after programme implementation, the DID estimate of the average programme impact (ATT) is:

$$ATT = E[Y_{t'}^1 - Y_t^0 | T = 1, \pi(X_t)] - E[Y_{t'}^0 - Y_t^0 | T = 0, \pi(X_t)] \quad (8)$$

Model 8 relies on a comparison of participants and non-participants before and after the programme implementation, which can be done using a simple t -test or through a regression-based approach.

4 | DATA AND EMPIRICAL IMPLEMENTATION

The impact of AES participation on farms' performance is evaluated separately for each country. We concentrate on two types of farming: farms specialised in field crops and farms specialised in conventional dairy production. This approach identifies the heterogeneous effects of AES across different EU member states and farming systems. In our empirical analysis, we rely on a balanced panel of farms covering the period 2006–2011 obtained from the Farm Accountancy Data Network. The FADN database is the most elaborated European data source and the only source of microeconomic data that is harmonised and comparable. The FADN data include structural and accountancy data of a large sample of farms and is often used to monitor income development and business activities of agricultural holdings in EU member states and allow evaluating the impact of the CAP. Farms that are monitored in the FADN sample are representative of the whole population of EU commercial farms according to the FADN regions, economic size, and type of farming systems. For crop farms, three EU countries are considered⁵: Germany, France and Italy. For dairy farms we use Germany, France and the Netherlands. For each country, the empirical analysis was conducted using balanced samples for field crops and dairy farms separately.

4.1 | Propensity score matching

For the purpose of performing propensity score matching,⁶ 2006 data were used to identify comparable treated farms and untreated farms based on observable variables. The year 2006—the year before the implementation of the 2007–2013 EU programming period—is considered to be the pre-treatment period,⁷ which means that for our analysis we focus on those farms that did not participate in any agri-environment schemes in 2006. Then, farms that did not receive environmental subsidies between 2007 and 2011 were assigned to the control group, and farms that did receive a payment during the programming period were assigned to the treated group.

The summary statistics for the main variables⁸ used in our empirical analysis are presented in Table 1. The total amount of agri-environmental payments included in the FADN system is summed into a single variable, which is quantified in euros. Unfortunately, no information is available on the type of scheme implemented by each farm or the share of the utilised agricultural land enrolled. The average value of agri-environmental payments received by farmers in our samples fluctuates from around €626 in France to €3303 in Germany for crops farms, whereas in dairy farms this range varies between €1581 in the Netherlands and €5809 in Germany. If we look at the average AES payment per hectare of UAA received by our sample farms, we find that dairy farms receive a higher rate than crop farms, with a range that goes from €14 per hectare in France to €23 per hectare for German dairy farmers. Field crops farmers for both countries received an average of €3.81 and €23 per hectare respectively.

Identifying which variables to use within the PSM model is a crucial decision when performing matching techniques. In the literature, there is still no agreed consensus about the choice of variables in the PSM model (Austin et al., 2007). Also, we recognise that including non-significant variables can affect the variance of the PSM estimator, although they do not bias or invalidate the estimates.

⁵We intended to consider further regions; however, our empirical approach is limited by data availability.

⁶Most schemes have a 5-year commitment duration, and participation is voluntary, meaning that farmers choose to participate based on utility considerations. Therefore, selection bias must be considered.

⁷The year 2011 is then considered to be the post-treatment period in the DID estimations. The post-intervention period is a key requirement for implementing DID methods.

⁸Some of the variables may coincide with the environmental damage indicators (pesticides, fertilisers and energy costs) that are used in the eco-efficiency estimation. The idea behind this choice is that there could be a significant variation in our sample in the use of pesticides and fertilisers between participating and non-participating farms. Whereas some farmers may be placing greater weight on environmental conservation, others may give more relevance to yield loss. This shows the necessity of including such variables in the matching procedure.

TABLE 1 Descriptive statistics of the main variables for the period 2006–2011 (whole sample, before and after matching)

	Field crops farms					
	Germany		France		Italy	
	Unmatched	Matched	Unmatched	Matched	Unmatched	Matched
Land (ha)	212 (409.4)	277 (578.5)	147.6 (85.3)	165.4 (89.5)	47.1 (66.5)	88.4 (85)
Labour (hours)	6859.9 (14,548.1)	5642.6 (8683.9)	3166.9 (3016.5)	3064.4 (2116.2)	3754.9 (4038.1)	4490.9 (3209.4)
Gross farm income (euros)	194,336.4 (366,014.7)	179,840.6 (313,965)	134,525.1 (11,0111.5)	147,998.5 (103,095.8)	75,989.6 (146,376.4)	109,533.4 (131,277.2)
Environmental subsidies (euros)	3303.9 (11,157.6)	2722.9 (7800.7)	626.2 (2165.5)	1280.6 (2918.2)	730.1 (4383.6)	5212.7 (11,043.2)
Crops output (euros)	324,718.1 (628,024.8)	247,350.3 (341,168.4)	208,816.6 (169,833.4)	196,605.3 (135,768.1)	93,213.5 (182,973.3)	123,623.5 (136,661.2)
Fertilisers (euros)	38,061.3 (65,108.3)	34,509.8 (51,339.5)	28,284.8 (19,104)	30,906.2 (20,351.6)	8055.6 (12,170.1)	13,487.4 (15,400)
Pesticides (euros)	30,838.5 (54,433.9)	27,959.7 (41,276.2)	22,948.6 (16,225.5)	24,354.9 (16,227.7)	5578.9 (10,911.5)	8584.0 (12,962.5)
Energy (euros)	28,573.3 (57,255.6)	25,356.1 (49,465.6)	11,639 (13,155.2)	11,902.4 (8870.6)	8232.3 (14,434.2)	12,012.6 (14,116.7)
Sample size	3426	1710	5232	1644	4296	444
	Dairy farms					
	Germany		France		The Netherlands	
	Unmatched	Matched	Unmatched	Matched	Unmatched	Matched
Land (ha)	201.2 (414.2)	204.3 (428.6)	99.3 (51.9)	93.9 (48.7)	58.6 (35.3)	61.3 (35.1)
Labour (hours)	11,612.3 (26,134.4)	12,166.7 (29,521.3)	3181.6 (1423)	3130.6 (1501.1)	4458.2 (1757.1)	4440.7 (1551.8)
Gross farm income (euros)	244,349.5 (485,009.9)	267,889.6 (544,325.7)	95,890.0 (58,787.5)	91,495.3 (54,269.3)	180,464.2 (148,777.9)	18,9961.9 (169,012.2)
Environmental subsidies (euros)	5809.9 (21,590)	3961.5 (16,173.7)	1613.6 (3313.9)	1257.6 (2574.1)	1581.4 (4283.3)	2828.4 (5591.4)
Milk (euros)	310,114.9 (558,090.7)	348,483.0 (645,573.1)	123,775.7 (67,992.1)	118,096.4 (62,626.8)	275,715.1 (188,612.2)	281,298.7 (190,321.5)
Number of cows	121.5 (204.6)	134.3 (237.7)	56.8 (24.5)	54.4 (22.6)	99 (60.8)	100.6 (63.7)
Fertilisers (euros)	21,816.4 (43,826.5)	23,384.5 (46,912.8)	10,560.5 (7548.3)	10,138.3 (7382.2)	8155.5 (5795.5)	8178.8 (5670.9)
Pesticides (euros)	11,950.4 (30,883.8)	12,898.4 (34,554.7)	5275.4 (4563.6)	5049.0 (4063.4)	2601.8 (3843.6)	1951.5 (1597.4)
Energy (euros)	41,818.9 (87,637.4)	43,718.9 (96,658.3)	9230.2 (5516.6)	8813.0 (5308.1)	13,880.2 (9194.3)	13,267.7 (8098.1)
Sample size	2406	1074	2166	996	984	456

Note: Standard deviations in parentheses.

Augurzky and Schmidt (2001) address the advantages and disadvantages of incorporating a large number of non-significant variables. They showed that using a smaller range of covariates can improve the treatment effect estimation. However, in two of their three testing sets, they intentionally include covariates that either do not or only weakly influence the outcome and variables that are relevant for the outcome but irrelevant to the treatment decision. The smallest and best performing set only includes covariates that influence both, which is a necessary condition for a successful matching procedure. In their conclusion, Augurzky and Schmidt (2001, p. 27) emphasise that ‘the main criterion of success for matching remains the balance of the relevant covariates and not the proper estimation of the selection equation’. In this context, Rubin and Thomas (1996) recommend including many variables even if some of them are not significant. Our variables selection differs slightly from one sample to another, however, in spite of the differences, our selection is based on theoretical economic arguments and empirical evidence (Arata & Sckokai, 2016; Chabé-Ferret & Subervie, 2013; Defrancesco et al., 2007; Matzdorf & Lorenz, 2010; Mennig & Sauer, 2020).

4.2 | The eco-efficiency model

To measure eco-efficiency ratings, we use data on economic value added and environmental indicators that reflect the environmental damage of farming activities. Economic value added is proxied by gross farm income,⁹ as defined in the FADN database. Regarding the environmental impacts, we rely on previous literature and select representative indicators that represent the damage of agricultural activities on the environment (Bonfiglio et al., 2017; Stepień et al., 2021). Specifically, we use three different proxies for the environmental damage caused by agriculture, namely farm's expenditure on fertilisers, pesticides and energy per hectare. We account for these inputs by using monetary units following the approach by Stepień et al. (2021). For the dairy sector, we also include stocking density (number of cows per hectare) as a (rather crude) proxy of both environmental damage and animal welfare.

Due to the insufficient environmental information provided by the FADN dataset, effect-based indicators (emissions, nutrient balances) cannot be quantified. The environmental damage is proxied here by the intensity of input use (cost per hectare). For instance, high levels of fertiliser application can lead to a large nitrogen surplus, and correspondingly large flows of nitrogen emissions and pollution. Similar assumptions apply to the use of pesticides and energy. We assume, for the lack of additional measures, that higher expenditures on inputs result in more pollution and environmental damage. The descriptive statistics of the sample used for our eco-efficiency analysis are shown in Table 2. Finally, in order to correctly account for the panel nature of the data, we run our eco-efficiency models for each year separately. This is relevant since the production frontier varies from year to year because of technological advances and weather conditions.

4.3 | Estimating average treatment effects

To investigate the effects of AES participation on eco-efficiency between 2006 and 2011, we measure the gap in the average change in the eco-efficiency scores between the participating and non-participating farms, indicating any effect of AES adoption on economic environmental performance. The average effect of AES on eco-efficiency has been calculated using a DID approach on the basis of the matched samples from the baseline data. Although we are not able to control for unobservable factors like managerial ability, motivation and environmental consciousness, we assume that these unobservable characteristics have a time-invariant impact on farm activities (Chabé-Ferret & Subervie, 2012), and hence are ‘differenced out’ in the DID.

⁹Gross farm income is calculated as the balance between earnings from total output (including total subsidies) and intermediate consumption. The latter includes total specific costs and farming overheads.

TABLE 2 Descriptive statistics of the variables used in the eco-efficiency analysis for the period 2006–2011 (matched sample)

	Field crops farms					
	Germany		France		Italy	
	Mean	St. dev.	Mean	St. dev.	Mean	St. dev.
Gross farm income (euros/ha)	1158	1382.1	841.8	827	1456.4	1626.2
Fertilisers (euros/ha)	132.7	68.3	136.6	61.7	106.6	64.5
Pesticides (euros/ha)	169.9	120.8	145.1	87.9	81.8	95.8
Energy (euros/ha)	160.7	165.3	63.6	37.6	141.9	107.4
Sample size	1710		1644		444	
	Dairy farms					
	Germany		France		The Netherlands	
	Mean	St. dev.	Mean	St. dev.	Mean	St. dev.
Gross farm income (euros/ha)	1352.4	721.3	852.5	312.7	2667.6	1092.1
Fertilisers (euros/ha)	84.7	39.3	80	41	93.3	30
Pesticides (euros/ha)	45.5	29.1	50.7	28.6	33.4	23
Energy (euros/ha)	192.7	74.2	81.1	29.8	192.1	74.0
Stocking density (Cows/ha)	0.9	0.4	0.6	0.2	1.6	0.4
Sample size	1074		996		456	

Note: All monetary variables were deflated to 2005 values using price indexes from Eurostat.

The DID can be implemented using a simple t -test or through a regression procedure, such as the following fixed-effects model:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta T_i + \delta t_i + (DID)T_i t_i + \eta_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (9)$$

where T is the treatment variable (that takes the value of one if the farm is an AES participant), t is the time dummy (that takes the value of zero for the year 2006 and one for the year 2011) and the coefficient of the interaction of T and t (DID) is the estimate for the impact of treatment on outcome Y , namely on a set of farm-level eco-efficiency scores. We conduct both analyses to cross-check and validate our results. A critical assumption with a basic DID estimator is that unobserved characteristics do not vary over time. The fixed-effects regression used in this study can control for unobserved time-invariant individual heterogeneity (η_i) that may also influence farm performance change.

5 | RESULTS

5.1 | Propensity score matching

The groups of covariates predicted to match participants and non-participants include both economic and regional aspects. The main variables are farm UAA, farm labour (working hours per hectare), farm gross income, crops and milk (for dairy farms) production intensity (sales per hectare), total assets per hectare, the intensity in fertilisers, pesticides and energy use (costs per hectare), stocking density in the case of dairy farms and share of rented land. Dummy variables are employed to represent regional heterogeneity, which makes it possible to take into account the different growing and climatic conditions.

For each country and both field crop and dairy farms, the propensity score was calculated using a logit regression as a measure of the probability that a farm will be classified as a programme participant. Logit model results for the propensity score matching are given in the Online Appendix

FIGURE 1 Distributions of average eco-efficiency scores for France, Germany and Italy (2006–2011, field crop farms) [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

(Tables A13–A18). The likelihood ratio tests for each sample are strongly significant, indicating that the overall models are statistically significant.

Propensity scores were calculated for each observation based on the parameter estimates of the logit model, which were then used to match participant and non-participant farms. Different matching algorithms¹⁰ were tested prior to selecting the specification that presents the best covariate balancing property. Before matching, significant differences are found between control and treated groups and, therefore, the resultant balance of the relevant covariates assesses the success of propensity score estimation. Tables A1 and A2 in the Online Appendix show the main covariates' mean values after matching, among non-participants and participants for the pre-treatment period (2006). The results suggest that there are no significant differences¹¹ between participating and non-participating farms after matching. We can therefore conclude that the matching algorithm controlled for observable differences.

5.2 | Eco-efficiency scores

Eco-efficiency scores are generated for both matched groups using DEA. The calculated average values of eco-efficiency for both field crop and dairy farms (participants and their matched non-participants) are reported in Table A3 in the Online Appendix. Figures 1 and 2 show the distributions of the average eco-efficiency scores.

For field crop farms, the results show that average eco-efficiency scores in our sample fluctuate from around 0.34 in Germany to 0.36 in France. As these results represent a radial distance from the best-practice frontier, this suggests that environmental damage reduction for field crop farmers could range from 64% ($1-0.36$) in France to 66% for German farmers. Among the three countries, only two French farms were determined to be fully eco-efficient. Figure 1 shows eco-efficiency density distributions for each of the three countries. The right-skewed distribution for France and Germany shows evidence that a large number of farms are positioned far from the best practice frontier. The eco-efficiency density distribution of the Italian farms would suggest the possibility of bimodal distribution with a larger group around 0.20 and a smaller group around 0.55. These results point to a low level of eco-efficiency among the three EU member states. One possible interpretation of low levels of eco-efficiency across these countries could be related to farmers' attitudes. Specifically, while some farmers may prioritise environmental preservation, others may prioritise production improvement and

¹⁰We tested the most common matching algorithms: kernel matching, radius matching and nearest neighbour matching without and with replacement from 1 to 10 neighbours. For each sample farm, we have compared different matching algorithms and selected the model that presents the smallest standardised bias.

¹¹Rosenbaum and Rubin (1985) recommend using the standardised bias (SB) when comparing between treated unit means and untreated unit means before and after matching as a measure of covariate balance. As noted by Oakes and Kaufman (2017), a standardised bias below 10% after matching would be seen as sufficient. Our findings indicate that the overall SB was reduced significantly for each sample by the matching technique.

FIGURE 2 Distributions of average eco-efficiency scores for France, Germany and the Netherlands (2006–2011, dairy farms) [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

crop loss prevention. This notion is consistent with previous evidence, suggesting that farmers over-use chemicals (Sexton et al., 2007; Singbo et al., 2015).

The average eco-efficiency score for the participating dairy farms and their matched controls varies slightly from around 0.63 in Germany to 0.65 in France. Despite the higher efficiency scores compared to crop farms, these results suggest that also in dairy production there is significant room for reducing environmental damages. Looking at the dairy farms fluctuating results across years (see Online Appendix, Table A4), one can explain these fluctuations by the existence of milk quota systems. If a farmer produces well above his quota in the first year and then reduces his output below the quota level in the second year, he triggers important differences in production efficiency from year to year (Schaper et al., 2010). Each of the three eco-efficiency density distributions reported in Figure 2 shows evidence of a uni-modal shape with a pronounced concentration of eco-efficiency scores around 0.6. This suggests that many dairy farms are operating this productive technology at a point where the scope for improvement in farms' environmental performance is considerable. The calculated radial eco-efficiency measures confirm recent findings on eco-efficiency in dairy production. Stepień et al. (2021) have used the FADN dataset to assess the eco-efficiency of small-scale farms in Poland and reported an average eco-efficiency score of 0.72 for dairy farms. By combining LCA and DEA to study eco-efficiency for a sample of 96 Galician dairy farms, Cortés et al. (2020) found an average eco-efficiency of 0.47. Similar results were obtained by Iribarren et al. (2011), with eco-efficiency scores ranging from 0.77 to 0.69.

5.3 | Average treatment effects

The results of the estimation of the AES on eco-efficiency are shown in the Online Appendix, Tables A7–A10, where the average effect of AES on radial and damage-specific eco-efficiency scores is calculated by comparing changes of eco-efficiency scores among participants and non-participants between 2006 and 2011.¹² We adopt a simple way to calculate the DID estimates by using a *t*-test to compare eco-efficiency scores between the two groups. A positive (negative) ATT represents an increase (decrease) in the mean eco-efficiency score of the participants that is greater than the increase (decrease) of their matched counterparts or that the decrease (increase) in the mean eco-efficiency score of the participants is lower than the decrease (increase) of the non-participants. The changes in eco-efficiency scores show the same increases or decreases in both participant and non-participant groups, with only two specific exceptions (pesticides in French dairy farms and fertilisers for Dutch dairy farms—in both cases the participants improve their scores whereas non-participants show a reduction between the years). In no case are these differences significant.

¹²Shorter periods were considered, but results did not change significantly

Our findings suggest that AES payment does not significantly affect overall or damage-specific eco-efficiency performance. France is one of the EU member states with a long tradition of agri-environment schemes. Two important schemes are implemented at the national level during the programming period 2007–2013 and were related to extensive grazing systems and diversification of arable crop rotations. The latter aims to reduce the need for pesticide inputs with longer intervals before a crop is repeated on the same plot, thus keeping some crop-specific pests under control. However, the effects of this scheme do not seem to be reflected in our eco-efficiency estimates.

The largest share of agri-environmental measures in Germany is related to grassland, arable land and organic farming (ART, 2016; IFLS, 2016; Thünen-Institut, 2016). However, with more than 100 separate sub-category measures available at the state level, farmers are paid for a wide variety of sustainability practices, not all related to input reduction. For instance, measures that aim to promote the implementation of diversified crop rotations often do not impose restrictions on the use of fertilisers or other chemicals, but limit the types of crops that may be grown. This heterogeneity, that cannot be accounted for when using FADN data, may be responsible for the absence of a significant impact. The same may well be true, especially when also considering the interaction between the AES and the cross-compliance instruments, in the other countries. Both policies aim at providing environmental benefits from agriculture, and as suggested by Bartolini et al. (2012) the linkage could lower the impact of one of the instruments, especially when both mechanisms are not well designed.

Our findings are also consistent with past research on the effectiveness of the agri-environment measures in the Netherlands, which failed to demonstrate the environmental benefits of the AES (Batáry et al., 2010; Kleijn et al., 2006).

In the results presented in Appendix Tables A7–A10, we rely on a *t*-test comparison of participants and non-participants before and after the programme implementation. However, as mentioned above, DID estimation can also be implemented within a regression framework. The results from the fixed effects model, confirming the *t*-test findings, are presented in the Online Appendix (Tables A11 and A12).

6 | CONCLUSION

Agri-environmental initiatives are central to the development of more resilient agricultural systems in Europe. Although there is empirical evidence on the environmental effectiveness of the schemes, there is limited empirical evidence on the combined environmental and economic impact of the schemes (Hasler et al., 2022). Here, focusing on the EU programming period 2007–2013, we assess the impact of agri-environmental payments on farm performance across four EU countries (Germany, France, Italy and the Netherlands) for crop and dairy farms. Our empirical analysis estimates the average treatment effect for AES participants using DID techniques. We combine our econometric analysis with a DAE approach to derive an estimate of eco-efficiency scores for each farm.

In terms of eco-efficiency, the scores from the radial and damaging input-specific specifications suggest that there is room for eco-efficiency improvements, both for crops and dairy farms, in all countries analysed here. The low eco-efficiency levels reflect the difficulty farmers have in balancing the need to produce marketable goods and the provision of public goods. Our results suggest that there is significant room for reducing environmental damage without reducing economic performance. As emphasised by Kuosmanen and Kortelainen (2005), policy measures that promote eco-efficiency might be typically easier to introduce because they normally do not restrict economic development while still reducing environmental damages.

Based on our DID results, we find that, on average, AES 2007–13 programme payments have no effect on either the overall or the damaging input specific eco-efficiency scores. The average change between 2006 and 2011 does not change significantly between participants and their matched non-participants, meaning that no observable difference is observed between participating and non-participating farms in the relationship between economic added value and environmental damage. The results suggest that farmers' participation in the AES did not significantly influence their management practices nor reduce use of fertilisers, pesticides and energy.

However, it is important for these findings to be contextualised. Reducing environmental damage by increasing resource use efficiency is not usually the main objective of the AES. Regional Rural Development Programmes fund a wide variety of measures, ranging from reduced input use to landscape or biodiversity management. Since the FADN database does not differentiate the AES payments by type of scheme, the heterogeneity in management practices cannot be accounted for in our analysis. As a result, the positive effects of low input schemes on farm eco-efficiency may well be obscured by schemes aimed at different objectives. We also note that the ecological effects of the schemes are not necessarily reflected in more efficient use of fertilisers, pesticides and energy. As such, we recognise that the lack of more direct indicators of environmental sustainability, such as greenhouse gas emissions, nitrogen balances or soil erosion rates (Kelly et al., 2018) is a limitation of our data. Future studies will need to combine FADN data with environmental information from national sources. Another explanation for our finding of insignificant effects of AES payments may relate to the fact that technical efficiency is not farmers' only concern. Indeed, some studies have identified a link between agricultural subsidies and a deterioration in farmer motivation toward more efficient production practices (Ahovi et al., 2021; Martinez Cillero et al., 2018; Skevas et al., 2012).

Nevertheless, from a policy perspective, we suggest that eco-efficiency measures can be a useful instrument to assess the contribution of AES in achieving the goals of the European agri-environmental policy. For example, it could be helpful to explore the use of eco-efficiency as a monitoring indicator for different types of AES, such as result-based schemes. Furthermore, pursuing improvements in eco-efficiency scores may be a cost-effective way to mitigate environmental impacts from farming, and increase the overall sustainability of farming activities while avoiding stringent management prescriptions. The responsible management of inputs is one of the cornerstones of the new CAP toward the achievement of these objectives (European Commission, 2022). The opportunities for performance improvements found in our analysis represent an interesting starting point for including eco-efficiency among the guiding criteria in the design of the new schemes.

In conclusion, despite the shortcomings associated with the currently available data, the proposed approach could be useful for further research into the environmental-economic impact of rural development policies. However, for future research, we suggest that more advanced or context-specific empirical models should be developed to assess the effects of specific AES on locally tailored farm-eco-efficiency measures.

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